

Title: Planning Grant: Building a community learning ecosystem for climate change resilience in Northern Colorado. PI Name: Lucinda Shellito, Earth & Atmospheric Sciences

Overview: The University of Northern Colorado (UNC) and Middle Path Ecosolutions propose **to develop climate change resilience in northern Colorado by founding a Climate Change Learning Ecosystem that will build capacity for local climate change adaptation strategies among UNC students and faculty, local institutions, and community members.** UNC is a teaching-focused institution, located in a region at the nexus of Food, Energy, and Water resource management with many underserved populations, creating a strategic area to study the development of climate resilience that integrates these sectors and voices in undergraduate-led community-engaged projects. Climate change solutions and adaptations require local buy-in to address issues within the community, and future generations (i.e., undergraduate students) will need to understand and connect climate change to diverse people, disciplines, and systems. Continuing to sustain human civilization critically depends on individuals from all backgrounds understanding what is happening in our natural and social environments and empowering them to make decisions that will ensure a sustainable future. However, there is presently a lack of structure for effective collaboration across academia, social institutions, and communities, inhibiting targeted action on projects that promote long-term sustainability. Learning Ecosystems provide this structure by creating a system of people, content, technology, culture, and strategy that impact formal and informal learning. As such, we propose the Learning Ecosystem process as a community-based approach that identifies problems and solutions within local spheres of influence to build climate change resilience. This planning grant proposes three phases. In Phase 1, the PIs will work with a community facilitator to map the local community landscape for building inclusive connections across disciplines and communities. Phase 2 will involve local situational analysis with community groups to identify climate-related issues that we have the capacity to address. Phases 1 and 2 will lay the groundwork for a summer institute (Phase 3) that brings together UNC faculty, students, and local community groups to learn from each other, identify strategies for addressing local climate challenges, and evaluate the need for an implementation grant.

Intellectual Merit: This project applies vetted approaches to build a learning ecosystem with synergies among UNC students, faculty, and diverse community stakeholders to build climate-change resilience. To this end, our objectives are to: (1) Identify how to prepare students to work with community stakeholders on local projects that build community resilience and adaptation to climate change impacts, (2) Build expertise about climate change among faculty from a broad array of disciplinary backgrounds, and (3) Develop resources and connections for community members and stakeholders to empower them to make decisions about challenges posed by climate-change impacts. The resources, activities, and outcomes developed through this process will contribute to assets and the body of knowledge concerning the efficacy and framework for building a learning ecosystem, thus being of merit to the scientific community and other stakeholders more broadly.

Broader Impacts: This project engages students, faculty, and community members from a wide range of backgrounds, ages, and levels of professional development with the goal of developing and documenting a learning ecosystem to support collaborative climate resilience projects and solutions. Ultimately, addressing complex, local climate-change related challenges depends on having all constituents at the table. Learning to facilitate collaboration among individuals with a broad range of voices and viewpoints is the first step in developing a long-term climate action plan. These activities form the foundation of future climate sustainability and interaction of currently disparate sectors and groups in northern Colorado. In addition, we aim to provide the momentum for self-determination of the learning ecosystem, so that this community has the self-efficacy and agency to innovate and develop their specific needs and goals. **After the end of the proposed project, we expect our fledgling learning ecosystem community to have a clear vision of how they want to move forward into the future.** Most importantly, we expect this learning ecosystem to have an understanding of how climate change will impact them individually and collectively in the northern Colorado community they can work with to build resilience to these impacts.

PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Overview

The future of our way of life critically depends on individuals from all parts of society to understand the critical change happening to our natural and social environments. While environmental monitoring and numerical modeling allow us to forecast impacts of climate change, without the buy-in and collaboration of broader society, it is difficult to make timely progress on climate action solutions. Thus, the aim of this proposal is to engage and empower University of Northern Colorado (UNC) students, faculty, and community stakeholders to help address the local challenges created by climate change, and shape a more sustainable, equitable world. Such work will help inform how other places can bridge the urgent gap between science and societal application. We propose to build capacity for an intentional Climate Resilience Learning Ecosystem at UNC that helps students, faculty, and local community members build a deeper understanding of climate change and its regional impacts in order to address imminent local challenges presented by climate change. **The goal of this planning grant is to use vetted principles to build a Learning Ecosystem that is composed of UNC students and faculty, and community members, and strengthens society-wide climate change education, resilience, and adaptation through community projects and stakeholder engagement.** To this end this work has three primary objectives:

1. Identify how to prepare students to work with community stakeholders on local projects that build community resilience to climate change impacts and ability to adapt.
2. Build expertise about climate change resilience among faculty from a broad array of disciplines.
3. Develop resources for community members to empower them to make decisions and take action around climate change challenges.

Regional Context

Why develop community systems of climate change resilience and adaptation in northern Colorado?

UNC is located in Greeley, Weld County, Colorado, which represents a nexus of key Food, Water, and Energy resources, creating a unique opportunity for implementing an action-oriented climate-change learning ecosystem. Weld County specializes in industries that both contribute to, and are affected by, climate change. Weld County has a booming oil and gas sector, one of the largest agricultural economies in the US, and a quickly expanding environmental and renewable energy sectors (Deloitte et al. 2018). Northern Colorado has a long history of farming and ranching, but increases in temperature and changes in water availability in the last few decades threaten crop yields and put into question the future of the agriculture industry (Kukul and Irmak, 2018). Increasing temperatures have also stressed Rocky Mountain forests and increased the likelihood for large fires, which impacts mountain tourism, resident homes, and northern Colorado air quality (Crooks et al., 2021). Greeley is one of the fastest growing cities in Colorado, and changes in water availability will likely impact continued expansion of housing developments (e.g., Polley et al., 2013; Wu et al., 2020; U.S. Census Bureau, 2020). Changes in snowpack, and thus, water availability, put enormous strain on the community overall (Ikeda et al., 2010; Ray et al., 2008).

In Weld County, there is a need to balance changing climate with demands for urban growth, as the region is one of the fastest-growing in the US for both population and economic growth (*Colorado Population Grew in Weld, Larimer Counties: 2020 Census Data*). Jobs most likely to be adversely affected by climate change (e.g., agricultural sector) are often held by under-resourced and/or marginalized community members (e.g., refugee, migrant, minority groups) and marginalized community members are more likely to be disproportionately affected by natural disasters (storms, floods) caused by climate change (Fothergill et al. 1999). Improving the connection between university resources and the needs and wisdom of the broader community is needed to find solutions for the looming climate change issues facing this region.

UNC is strategically positioned to serve as the nexus for a Learning Community focused on addressing local impacts of climate change and amplifying minoritized voices in the community. As of Fall 2020, 23.4

% of UNC's undergraduate population identified as Hispanic/Latinx. The university is seeking to become a Hispanic Serving Institution within the next five years (requires minimum 25 % Hispanic population). In the PIs' home units, Geography, GIS, and Sustainability and Earth and Atmospheric Sciences, graduates fill positions within sectors that contribute to building a sustainable and equitable future, including working in environmental compliance, environmental consulting, wildlife and park management, mining, energy industries, and climate and weather prediction. Faculty operate under a teacher-scholar model, whereby undergraduates are directly included in the research process. The PIs and their programs will serve as a central hub from which to build climate-change Learning Ecosystem efforts.

Developing a Climate Resilience Learning Ecosystem (CCLE) for northern Colorado: Long-standing 'top-down' approaches, in which the curriculum is developed and then disseminated broadly, is increasingly being replaced by more 'bottom-up' approaches, in which everyone involved in education, from students to community members, is involved in the development of a curriculum (Fadeeva et al., 2014). As opposed to *passive* learning environments where a teacher or dominant actor provides all the answers, 'flipped classroom' and participant-centered approaches represent *intentional* learning approaches to support new patterns of interaction and communication between faculty, students and community members to overcome the inertia of conventional academic institutions (Brundiers et al., 2014) and hierarchical dominance in learning models. Such new models of learning are needed to move us forward quickly toward finding ways to adapt to climate change. Thus, we adopt a model of student-faculty-community co-creation and collaboration in curriculum development (Nam and Lee, 2020) that moves from *passive* learning experiences for students, faculty and community members, to an *intentional* learning ecosystem (Manning, 2020) with UNC acting as a hub for the connected communities (Fig 1). This intentional learning ecosystem will consist of connected people, content, technology, culture, and co-developed strategies, all of which has an impact on both the formal and informal learning that occurs in our communities.

Figure 1. UNC will be the hub for a Learning Ecosystem focused on local climate change impacts.

Building a sustainable community organization: A key feature of this proposal centers around the development of a sustainable community organization, initially focused on the question "What does climate resilience look like for our community?". This would be driven by using an online community-building approach termed as "community activation" (Virapongse, 2021), which emphasizes the intentional learning of a community. With such an approach, the goal of community building is to help the community meet its own needs; governance and organizational structures are created to enable community members to more easily self-organize, mobilize, and support their self-determination. Rather than creating reliance and dependence on any one person, like a community manager, a community activation approach frames a community manager's role as a facilitator and orienter who strives to pull themselves out of the center of a given community (i.e., leading from behind; Scharmer, 2009). Key personnel Virapongse is a community building consultant (Community Builder) who developed the community activation approach. Virapongse applies this community building approach among organizations that aim to be more inclusive of and better aligned to their broader communities, such as by implementing decentralized approaches like peer governance (Bollier and Helfrich, 2019). One example of where the community activation approach has been highly successful is in the development of the Ronin Institute (a global community of independent scholars, Ronin Institute 2022). Because the "community activation" approach aims for mobilization and empowerment of the participating members of a community, the long-term cost of maintaining such a community is quite low.

TABLE 1: Logic Model / Program Process

Resources/Inputs	Activities	Outputs / Outcomes
<i>Phase 1 (Year 1: May 2023-May 2024): Landscape Mapping to Build Connections & Community</i>		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Teaching Climate Change UNC Faculty Learning Community -Students and Student Groups -Community Members and Organizations -Community Builder - Evaluator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -With Community Builder, identify initial core stakeholders to invite to the Learning Ecosystem -With Community Builder , develop criteria for individuals and groups to engage with the Learning Ecosystem -With Community Builder , determine and initiate communication strategy for group -Workshop 1: Facilitated workshop with initial members of the Learning Ecosystem to determine major community concerns and problems needing to be solved; establish Draft Mission Statement 	<p><i>Outputs:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Preliminary Learning Ecosystem -Draft mission statement -Ecosystem goals <p><i>Outcomes:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initial community groups are connected and engaged with each other through the Learning Ecosystem - Initial community groups have shared knowledge of concerns, problems to be solved, and understand the capacity and needs of the community moving to solve these problems.
<i>Phase 2 (Year 2: May 2024-May 2025): Situation Analysis by Engaging with the Community:</i>		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Preliminary Learning Ecosystem and Mission -Community Builder -Evaluator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - With Community Builder and external evaluator, identify strengths and weaknesses of Preliminary Learning Ecosystem stakeholder portfolio and determine whether we wish to invite additional groups to the Ecosystem- Collaboratively evaluate and revise mission statement and value propositions - Workshop 2: Facilitated value mapping workshop to determine Learning Ecosystem goals/objectives and governance framework and decision-making strategies - Develop Learning Ecosystem Institute 	<p><i>Outputs:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Final Learning Ecosystem -Final Mission statement -Ecosystem goals -Ecosystem decision-making strategies -Draft plans for Learning Ecosystem Institute <p><i>Outcomes:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Additional community members join the group with the same outcomes as Phase 1 - Members of the Learning Ecosystem all have buy in to the project
<i>Phase 3: Solidify the Learning Ecosystem via Summer institute (May-December 2025)</i>		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Learning Ecosystem Framework -Community Builder -Evaluator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Finalize plans for Learning Ecosystem Institute - With Community Builder, host Climate Change Learning Ecosystem (CCLE) Institute - At Institute, evaluate and revise community governance and policies - At Institute, evaluate and plan next steps and need for implementation grant 	<p><i>Outputs:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Final Learning Ecosystem framework, community governance and policies -Plans for Implementation Grant <p><i>Outcomes:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Learning Ecosystem is a functional, active, and self-governing entity with many connected communities

To achieve a mature and healthy “activated” community, the following aspects will be developed during the project (Table 1): governance and decision-making structure, communication approaches (both internal and external), infrastructure (such as a website, Slack workspace, and any other needed platforms to help the community interact), events (such as community events that typically occur at least once a month), and documentation (of the processes developed and adhered to by the community). Community building will include these steps 1. Understanding the community; 2. Bringing community together; 3. Developing governance and organizational structure of the community; and 4. Enabling and empowering the community. Each of these aspects is described in detail in each of the phases below.

PROJECT DESIGN

This planning grant supports a 3-phase development of a summer institute that brings together students, faculty, and community members engaged in addressing local challenges posed by climate change.

Phase 1 (Year 1: May 2023-May 2024): Landscape Mapping to Build Connections & Community

- Objective 1: Establish preliminary Learning Ecosystem with existing network
- Objective 2: Draft mission statement and value proposition
- Objective 3: Define membership in the Learning Community
- Objective 4: Determine norms for engagement and initiate communication strategy for group

One key challenge of this community building effort is to invoke an easy-to-understand value proposition that compels people to join and volunteer their time to participate and lead. We propose to organize our community around this value proposition and develop a clear mission statement in Phase 1 (Year 1). In Phase 1 we will work with the Community Builder to identify and engage with groups and community members on and off campus to be part of our learning ecosystem, starting with an initial list of existing connections and known entities that include other faculty, local advocacy groups, and engagement institutions such as the agricultural extension office. The focus of Phase 1 will be to *Understand the community*, which consists of identifying the strengths and needs of local community groups, faculty and students, and looking for areas of consensus and constraints. Understanding the Community includes events like workshops and online meetings, as well as one-on-one and small group discussions between the PIs and Key personnel of this proposal as we strive to understand the needs, constraints, and goals of the different sub-discipline and data system communities. In addition, we will seek to map the landscape of northern Colorado communities that should be included in this proposed learning ecosystem.

At UNC we have a Teaching Climate Change Faculty Learning Community with 13 faculty members across campus (including humanities and business faculty), as well as sustainability and climate focused student groups such as Earth Guardians (local chapter of a national network), and Student Leadership for Environmental Action Fund. The PI team has met with representatives from the local chapter of the Citizen’s Climate Lobby, who are working to establish sustainability boards in local municipalities to address climate resilience and community sustainability efforts and have provided a letter of support for this proposal. To develop this network *further*, we want to bring together our existing connections to identify what other voices should be included and establish criteria for who should be in the room. Some examples already discussed include sectors such as the hemp industry, meat packers, parents, car enthusiast groups, the K12 education community, and also including diverse representation such as different education levels and demographics. We will expand our network and connectivity during this phase and identified groups will be invited to continue into Phase 2 of the project where we will also continue to identify groups and people for project development.

To be a community, individuals within the community must have easy access to each other, build trust, and be able to interact and work together without the presence of a facilitator (community manager) or a structure such as an event. To accomplish this, we will seek input from the community (at workshops)

about the best ways to interact, working to empower members with agency to engage in our Learning Ecosystem on their own terms. Options include creating a simple website with instructions about how to “join the community”, developing a mailing list through MailChimp to implement regular communication about the project, a Slack workspace that is moderated by the community manager, and/or a collaborative documentation workspace such as a google drive. As each sub-discipline and data system community workshop and associated events are conducted, all of the participants, their network, and interested individuals will be invited to join the mailing list and Slack workspace.

Phase 2 (Year 2: May 2024-May 2025): Building a Community of Practice: Situation Analysis & Governance

- Objective 5: Develop Governance Framework and Decision-Making Strategies
- Objective 6: Collaboratively evaluate and revise mission statement and value propositions
- Objective 7: Develop goals/objectives for the Learning Ecosystem and Institute
- Objective 8: Develop Learning Ecosystem Institute

In Phase 2 of this project, we will begin the discussion around sustainability of the community, and what it might look like (Table 1). One option, for example, could be to incorporate with established communities like the active Citizen’s Climate Lobby and Western Resource Advocates organizations, which share a similar mission as this proposed project. To explore these options, we will broaden our participation outside of the scope of our academic and scientific communities by interacting and/or collaborating with leaders from these adjacent established communities and attending their community meetings. As the community matures (membership grows and activity increases), the PIs and key personnel of this proposal and core members of the Learning Ecosystem will begin to lead the governance development of the community. As such, one or two community meetings will be held to brainstorm governance ideas and establish how community input will be integrated into the community. Part of the governance development will include identifying initial community leaders to lead initiatives that are key to the development of the community and individual self-efficacy (as determined by the community). We will follow community guidelines to identify local challenges that require long term monitoring and solutions. Specifically, we will build shared knowledge and bring science into value conversations. This may involve gathering local data and sharing that data through construction of climate story maps, led by our student work. During this process we will also continue to identify groups and people for involvement in the Learning Ecosystem. In Phase 2 we will also prepare for the summer institute. Curriculum for the institute will be co-developed by faculty, students and community members in a series of short workshops that follow-on from the community governance discussions. As a community we will decide on learning objectives for participants that are appropriate for expertise and career stage.

Phase 3: Solidify the Learning Ecosystem via Summer institute (May-December 2025)

- Objective 9: Host Learning Ecosystem Institute
- Objective 10: Evaluate and revise community governance and policies
- Objective 11: Evaluate and plan next steps and need for CTGC Implementation Grant

In the summer of Year 2.5, we will host a Climate Change Learning Ecosystem institute that will bring together a cohort of students, faculty, and community members invited from communities identified during Phase 1 and 2 to address specific problems identified in Phase 2. These participants will include, but not be limited to, the Learning Ecosystem members. Student participants will be chosen through a competitive application process (with priority for minoritized and underrepresented students). They will be provided with a stipend for their participation. The PIs will help students navigate and assess their interactions and experiences through the learning ecosystem with a focus on student experience and supporting students in their own *reflection* of the experience. Participating faculty will also receive a stipend for participation, and are considered an integral part of the cohort. This phase will also focus on fine-tuning the “rules” of the community, and moving forward any community documentation or processes.

Community members will also be deepening the work on any of the collaborative sub-group projects that are expected to arise as a result of the community interacting together. These sub-group projects and the overall Learning Ecosystem will also be evaluated for potential development of a CTGC implementation grant proposal for submission to NSF.

Summer Institute Follow-up (Year 2.5: Summer-Fall 2025)

Following the summer institute, we will have three virtual meetings with all participants to continue the cohort. At these meetings participants will share outcomes of ongoing project activities and long-term learning goals. There will also be a couple of follow-up meetings with students to provide ongoing professional development.

PROJECT PERSONNEL

The diverse all-women team consists of:

PI Lucinda Shellito will use her expertise in climate science and in leading professional development programs to build a workshop framework that will serve to forge connections between participants from diverse backgrounds. Her scientific research experience has focused on using numerical models to simulate warm climates in Earth's deep past, and, more recently, in understanding the impacts of modern global warming on tropical mountains, through her work as a Fulbright scholar in Ecuador. Educational interests involve research on using numerical and conceptual models to facilitate inquiry and learning among students and the development of societally-relevant science curricula. She has extensive experience serving as a workshop developer and facilitator at her home institution and nationally and internationally through the National Association of Geoscience Teachers. She has delivered workshops on a range of topics from curriculum development and program planning, developing engaging teaching strategies on technical topics, and promoting inclusivity and equity in the classroom.

Co-PI Sharon Bywater-Reyes teaches hydrology and soils and makes linkages among climate change, surface processes, and communities. She has many community-based environmental projects with diverse stakeholders and has built connections with the local K-12 district. She has been a facilitator for Teaching for Equity and Inclusion workshops. She is thus well suited for bringing together diverse stakeholders, sharing technical knowledge, and identifying community-based solutions to environmental problems. She will aid the facilitator in networking, compiling scientific knowledge, communicating with stakeholders, and all products from the workshop. She additionally has experience in sharing open-source curricular materials and linking assessment data to outcomes of objectives. She will aid in analyzing and dissemination products and data from the project.

Co-PI Chelsie Romulo will serve as an expert in environmental science and education. Her research expertise includes leading an NSF IUSE funded project for developing an assessment tool for evaluating teaching and learning of complex Food-Energy-Water concepts. Currently she facilitates the co-development and implementation of curriculum for a year-long faculty professional development program to build more inclusive STEM courses. Romulo will support and co-conduct networking and workshop development activities, including development of instruments, data collection, analysis, and dissemination of products given her experience and expertise in STEM education research, the discipline of conservation science, and STEM Education Inclusive curriculum development.

Consultant (Community Builder) Arika Virapongse has expertise in community-building, which she shares as a consultant at Middle Path EcoSolutions—a woman-owned, minority-owned small business that helps organizations build their communities. She is the Co-Chair of the Community Resilience cluster at Earth Science Information Partners that explores the connection between Earth Science and community resilience. Virapongse is the Community Director at the Ronin Institute for Independent Scholarship, where she implements a community activation process across its 400+ global membership.

Consultant (External Evaluator) Rupanwita Gupta is a conservation psychologist and Owner of Rupu Gupta Consulting. She specializes in mixed-methods research and evaluation, with expertise in inclusive practices and culturally responsive approaches in the environmental movement. Her recent work focuses on STEM learning in informal spaces and partnership building processes in community focused climate resilience efforts. Dr. Gupta was Co-PI of the evaluation of the Third National Climate Assessment. She has led evaluation of the National Wildlife Federation’s Resilience in School Consortium Phase II NOAA ELP program and evaluation studies of the New England Aquarium’s community resilience partnerships. She is Co-Chair of the Community Resilience Cluster within Earth Science Information Partners. She has led evaluation efforts of the EPA-funded EE Capacity project, as well as Children and Nature Network’s Green Schoolyards for Healthy Communities Initiative.

EVALUATION AND REPORTING

External evaluation of the Climate Resilience Learning Ecosystem project will be led by Key Personnel Rupanwita Gupta, PhD, Owner of Rupu Gupta Consulting. The evaluation will follow the tenets of developmental evaluation (Patton, 2011) via a collaborative approach with timely responsiveness and feedback. Additionally, attention to a utilization focused approach (Patton, 2008) will ensure that the design, focus, and results align with the intended use of the findings. All evaluation activities will be conducted with approval from an external Institutional review board. Qualitative methods will be employed, drawing on best practices (Onwuegbuzie and Collins, 2007), cultural responsiveness to ensure respect of stakeholder circumstances and expertise, (Pipi et al., 2004; Smith, 2005). The evaluation will assess how the project builds a multi-stakeholder learning ecosystem (comprising students, faculty, community groups) to learn about and tackle climate resilient priorities in northern Colorado. It will examine the following key questions about how the learning ecosystem will enable students, faculty and community groups to:

- Respectfully engage in equitable exchange and learning
- Grow their knowledge base about local climate resilient priorities
- Build their agency, self-efficacy, and personal resilience in collaborating on local issues
- Co-develop community-focused projects to build climate resilience in northern Colorado

A community of practice (CoP) framework will inform the study (Wenger et al. 2011); where a CoP is defined as “a learning partnership among people who find it useful to learn from and with each other about a particular area”, in this case local climate resilience issues. We will use the different cycles in the evolution of a CoP (e.g., Immediate value through activities and interactions; Potential value by growing knowledge capital; Applied value when using lessons to change existing practice) to understand how the project helps members learn and be empowered. Personal resilience will be informed by work on optimism and hope for environmental work (Ojala, 2012) and personal resilience to engage in environmental work (Gupta et al. 2021). The learning ecosystem’s engagement among a group with multiple interests and expertise, will be assessed to understand how they develop shared goals and understandings of local climate priorities in respectful and culturally responsive ways (e.g., Gupta, et al. 2017); appreciate different perspectives on environment-focused work (Fraser et al. 2014); conceptualize and build climate justice for a resilient community (Cutter et al. 2008).

Initial assessment of CoP (Year 1): The evaluator will work closely with the project team during the planning phase to understand the project context better and plan out the evaluation activities, including attending regular meetings with the project leads. Once the learning ecosystem has been established and a mission statement/value proposition has been developed, a set of three focus groups (each with (6-8) x 3, total = 18-24 people) will be conducted with mixed groups of members to learn about the process of partnership development (Kitzinger, 1994). Questions will ask about how their expectations have unfolded, including their collaborative work with the others. Common questions will be asked of all focus group participants, with specific ones for different roles. Analysis of the focus group will identify how the CoP helped create a foundation to develop equitable partnership processes for different groups of members.

Continued assessment of CoP (Year 2): Another set of three mixed focus groups will continue to assess how the CoP evolves and creates opportunities for equitable learning. Apart from similar questions from the previous year about the growth of the CoP, and their learning, additional ones will ask members to reflect on their sense of agency, perception of community focused changed agents, and self-efficacy (Sherer et al, 1982) as they co-develop plans among themselves. A short end of year report will document the findings at the end of Years 1 and 2 and make recommendations for refinement.

Workshop assessment (Year 3): Observations of the workshop and embedded evaluation (McCowan and McCowan, 1999) activities (in collaboration with the project team) will be used to study how the workshop provides additional opportunities for shared learning and planning for future activities. A focus group will be conducted with a group of participants to assess their end of project learning, their perceptions of the CoP, and their anticipated future role in it. A **Final Report** will compare findings over the project duration and document the value of the CoP to build a foundation for equitable climate resilience work in northern Colorado.

BROADER IMPACTS

This project engages students, faculty, and community members from a wide range of backgrounds, ages, and levels of professional development with the goal of developing and documenting a learning ecosystem to support collaborative climate resilience projects and solutions. Ultimately, addressing complex, local climate-change related challenges depends on having all constituents at the table. Learning to facilitate collaboration among individuals with a broad range of voices and viewpoints is the first step in developing a long-term climate action plan. The activities form the foundation of future climate sustainability and interaction of currently disparate sectors and groups in northern Colorado. In addition, we aim to provide the momentum for self-determination of the learning ecosystem, so that this community has the self-efficacy and agency to innovate and develop their specific needs and goals. **After the end of the proposed project, we expect our fledgling learning ecosystem community to have a clear vision of how they want to move forward into the future.** Another key result is that the hired community manager will have the skill set, familiarity with the community, and social capital (through networking and experience) to be a resource for future community development activities in the broader climate change community. Most importantly, we expect that this learning ecosystem community will have an understanding of how climate change will impact themselves and other groups in northern Colorado and who in our community they can work with to build resilience to these impacts. After the completion of this project, we anticipate a more “activated” community, defined as a community that takes ownership of processes developed in the project and spinning off to use those processes to meet their goals within the framing of their context. The incorporation and engagement of all groups and the challenge to create a structure that will allow for continued cooperation and leadership in northern Colorado will be the focus of this project. We expect to see consistent or growing activity in our collaborative community spaces with new members joining the community, and new individuals taking on leadership roles. Broad engagement, problem solving, transparency, and sustained shared governance and vision will be the hallmarks of this effort.